

SS 82, AMENHUTEP II TEMPLE; LOCATE POINTS
DM 501

THIS PAGE SURVEY STATION N2970/E520

① SD 16.270
16.261
16.270
V = 99.3803^G
H = 154.5822^G
D = 16.269

⑥ ~~37.534~~ 27.463
~~11.523~~ 27.514 } 27.51
27.555
V 104.0699
H 208.980
D 27.45

⑫ 19.681
19.682
V 99.2427
H 162.9186
D 19.679

② 37.924
SD 37.88
37.924
V 97.7216
H 151.5919
D = 37.899

⑦ 21.513
21.520 } 21.513
21.506
V 101.2673
H 193.6327
D = 21.508

⑬ 26.640 } 26.657
26.671 }
26.666 }
V 99.1005
H 159.1236
D 26.654

③ 42.846 }
SD: 42.841 } 3:42.837
42.808 }
42.831 }
V 99.7976
H 164.9784
D = 42.838

⑧ 20.205
20.201
V 101.2812
H 188.8793 - sighted bottom
actual point
D 20.20

⑭ 25.501 } AV
25.478 } 25.492
V 99.4419
H 165.286
D 25.491

④ 47.788 }
SD: 47.763 } 47.763
47.738 }
V 101.062
H 182.3577
D 47.756

⑨ 18.534 }
18.521 } 18.530
18.534 }
V 99.3591
H 170.9152
D = 18.529

⑮ 20.478 21.658
20.698 21.678
20.694
V 99.1241
H 170.1589
D 21.6759

⑤ 30.044
30.048
AV 30.02
V 105.032
H 210.7402
D 29.926

⑩ 17.673 }
17.681 } 17.677
V 97.1498
H 157.8628
D = 17.6592

⑯ 22.752 } 22.755
22.764 }
22.751 }
V 95.6283
H 177.9883
D 22.701

⑪ 20.201 }
20.214 } 20.207
V 100.0896
H 168.8488
D = 20.2069

⑰ 21.502
V 98.853
H 180.3478
D 21.4985

⑱ 22.530 } 22.531
22.532 }
22.531 }
V 101.1392
H 185.0789
D 22.527

5582, AMENHOTEP II TEMPLE POINTS
LOCATION DM501

N2970/E520

(19) 31.823
31.821
√ 100.1192
H 181.0064
D 31.820

(20) 30.454 }
30.431 } 30.4425
√ 100.4978
H 175.324
D 30.441

(21) 29.695
29.694
√ 100.0718
H 170.7778
D 29.694

(22) 35.340 }
35.322 } 35.331
√ 99.5458
H 101.2669
D 35.330

(23) 34.962 }
34.951 } 34.956
√ 99.6082
H 158.4022
D 34.955

(24) 26.873 }
28.626 } 28.628
28.630 }
√ 98.9925
H 157.3332
D 28.624

(25) 29.30
29.31
√ 99.3342
H 164.4106
D 29.298

(26) 31.654
31.652
√ 100.186
H 163.1744
D 31.653

(27) 34.814
34.810
√ 98.8705
H 167.2024
D 34.804

(28) 36.711
√ 100.2506
H 176.2599
D 36.71

(29) 32.30
√ 98.8142
H 180.623
D 32.294

(30) 39.386
39.368
√ 98.7382
H 154.9768
D 39.36

(31) 36.570 }
36.574 } 36.58
√ 97.4642
H 158.2905
D 36.578

(32) 37.215 }
37.224 } 37.217
√ 100.4306
H 182.5622
D 37.218

(33) 39.361
39.360
√ 99.9374
H 180.2936
D 39.359

(34) 44.645 }
44.656 } 44.65
√ 99.9533
H 180.6238
D 44.649

(35) 41.566
41.564
√ 100.1674
H 180.9533
D 41.565

(36) 28.120 }
28.114 } 28.117
√ 100.6388
H 196.2644
D 28.115

(37) 29.032 }
29.014 } 29.023
√ 101.1346
H 202.7070
D 29.01

(38) 25.456, 25.446 } 25.451
√ 100.7416
H 190.3842
D 25.449

N2970/E490

(39) 18.186 }
18.223 } 18.204
√ 84.5
H 281.3944
D 17.66

(40) √ 83.9542
H 283.5364
SD 17.21
D 16.66